

PROBLEMS OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN FICTION

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Abstract: This article discusses the theory is put forward that literature, the work of the masters of the artistic word is the main source of upbringing and education. The word "concept" is subjected to a deep linguistic and philological analysis, which in the pedagogical sense acquires additional shades of semantic meaning. It is also advisable to use the phrase "pedagogical concept" when analyzing a literary text in depth and defining the pedagogical views of a particular writer. The article provides methods for determining the pedagogical concept of a writer.

Keywords: writer-teacher, view, conclusion, concept, idea, text, system of views, concept, poet-teacher,.

Introduction. Concept is a complex cognitive linguasocial construct, the use of which by us as a foreign-language term should be justified. It is associated with the concept of "concept", which, according to the definition of M.M. Angelova, "is the core term of the conceptual apparatus of cultural linguistics. The lexical and phraseological level of language is recognized as a priority, on which the facts of the material and, accordingly, spiritual culture of man are most clearly recorded in symbolic form, and in general the value orientations of a particular society, the system of its moral, ethical and aesthetic preferences are reflected" [1, p. 3-10].

Analysis of literature and methods. Having studied the concept, we came to the idea that a number of scientists (E.S. Kubryakova, N.A. Boldyrev, I.A. Sternin, A.P. Babushkin) interpret the concept as a unit of operational consciousness, acting as a holistic, undivided reflection of a fact of reality. Formed in the process of mental construction (i.e. conceptualization) of objects and phenomena of the surrounding world, concepts reflect the content of knowledge, experience, results of all human activity and the results of his cognition of the surrounding world in the form of certain units of knowledge. The main concepts develop into the concept that we study as one of the key concepts of our work. Therefore, we studied the nature of this concept. And here is what we discovered.

In the "Dictionary of Terms in General and Social Pedagogy" by A.S. Voronin we read: "A concept is a system of views on certain phenomena, a guiding idea, a defining character of cognitive and practical activity, a main idea or leading intention, an interpretation of a phenomenon, a basic point of view" [11]. As we can see, here "concept" is interpreted both as a system of views and, at the same time, as a guiding idea, a leading thought or a point of view on a particular problem.

The definition of "concept" by A.S. Voronin almost coincides with the definition in the "Pedagogical Dictionary by Topics" by L.P. Rusinova: "A concept is a set of ideas, views, principles that reflect the basic knowledge of scientists about the essence of a phenomenon." The first thing that catches our eye when comparing the definitions of A.S. Voronin and L.P.

Rusinova is that in the second case, instead of the word "system", "collectivity" is used, which makes the definition more relaxed, as a result of which the strict meaning that was given with the help of the concept of "system" is lost here. "Collection" is also collected together, but without any specific order, without purposefulness. Let us refer to the explanatory dictionary of L.F. Ilyichev: "Collection is a combination, union, general result of something" [13]. In the same dictionary, "system" is explained as follows: "1. A certain order in the arrangement and connection of parts of something, in actions. 2. The form of organization of something. 3. Something whole, representing the unity of regularly arranged and mutually interconnected parts" [13]. From these explanations we immediately notice that the "concept" is closer to the concept of "system" and differs from "set". Having compared the explanations, we are convinced that the "set" concept is more free, general, does not require regularity, as if chaotically "collected in one heap". And the "system" is a strict lawful organization of ideas, the interrelation of parts, some of which are leading, others complement or explain the first, without losing their significance and having their place in this sequence.

Thus, we can say that in the "Pedagogical Dictionary by Topics" "concept" is interpreted as a random set of phenomena that do not have anything in common with each other. We think that such a definition has nothing to do with such a serious scientific concept.

In the "Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary" we read: "Concept is a leading idea, a certain way of understanding, interpreting some phenomenon; "the sudden birth of an idea, main thought, artistic or other motive" [8]. Two points are distinguished here: 1) the concept is the leading idea; 2) the concept is a suddenly born idea.

Here we find an indication of an artistic motive. From the point of view of the "Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary", even an unexpectedly arising idea, fleeting sparks of thought are capable of turning into a leading idea, that is, a concept. It is also noteworthy that "concept" is interpreted here as a concept that incorporates everything that concerns a particular idea or concept.

In the definition of the "Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary", one more point attracts attention - an artistic motive. This means that "concept" is not only a philosophical, political phenomenon; this concept can be applied to artistic phenomena.

We see a rather lengthy explanation of the "concept" in the "Sociological Encyclopedia": "Concept - (Latin *conceptio* understanding, single idea, leading thought) a system of views expressing a certain way of seeing (point of view), understanding, interpreting any objects, phenomena, processes and presenting the leading idea or (and) constructive principle, realizing a certain idea in one or another theoretical practice... Thus, the concept is first of all introduced into the theoretical discourses of disciplines by their initial principles and premises, defining the basic concepts-concepts and reasoning schemes, forming fundamental questions (ideas), in correlation with which special statements built within these discourses receive their meaning and justification" [14]. As we can see, here, in contrast to previous interpretations, the concept of "concept" is associated with a system, at the same time the idea is emphasized that the leading idea or principle is derived and "presented" from this system. According to this explanation, the concept implements a certain idea, i.e. is implemented. It concerns a certain area and is programmatic in solving a clearly defined problem. It is also worth noting that the concept is linked to the "personal principle", the connection of its content with the figure of the founder, who is the sole owner of the original idea. This is of no

small importance in the study of the pedagogical views of a specific writer, as in our case. As noted, the concept is also necessary for a more detailed elaboration of the proposed idea.

The "Modern Encyclopedia" defines "concept" as follows: "a certain way of understanding, interpreting any phenomena, the main point of view, the guiding idea for their illumination; the leading idea, the constructive principle of various types of activity." As we can see, the explanation does not begin with the "leading idea", as we have already noticed in most interpretations, but with the phrase "in a certain way". And the idea of systematicity is not emphasized, as was observed in the above explanations.

For comparison, we will provide an interpretation of the concept of "concept" from the Fundamental Electronic Library, where the meaning of "concept" is taken from the "Dictionary of the Russian Language" edited by A.P. Evgenyeva: "A system of views on a particular phenomenon that are interconnected and follow from each other. The main thought, idea of a work, essay, etc." [9]. As we can see, here "concept" is interpreted narrower than in the previous source. However, this definition cannot be ignored, because it notes the systematic nature of views and their connection with each other.

In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language" edited by D.N. Ushakov, a concept is defined as "an idea, a theoretical construction; one or another understanding of something." Here, too, we see a very narrow interpretation of the concept under study.

In the "Dictionary of the Russian Language" by S.I. Ozhegov, it is noted: "A system of views on something; the main idea."

In the "Pedagogical Dictionary and Reference Book," the concept of "Concept" is given the following interpretation: "Concept - 1) a system of views on processes and phenomena in nature and society; 2) a leading idea that determines the strategy of action in the implementation of reforms, programs, projects, plans." Based on the interpretations of the "Pedagogical Dictionary and Handbook", we can derive the following definition: a concept (or system) is a system of views on a set of interconnected methods and processes necessary to exert a targeted influence on an individual to cultivate moral qualities in him.

The Dictionary of Foreign Languages notes: "Concept - 1) a system of views, one or another understanding of phenomena, processes; 2) a single, defining concept, the leading idea of any work, scientific work." In this interpretation, the idea of "systematicity", the defining concept, also dominates. It is interesting that the interpretation comes down to the leading idea of a work, scientific work. The interpretation of the concept of "concept" in a number of other sources is close to the above-mentioned definitions, in particular, in the "Encyclopedia of Epistemology and Philosophy of Science", "The Great Psychological Encyclopedia", "Encyclopedia of Sociology", "Historical Dictionary of Gallicisms of the Russian Language", "Etymological Dictionary of the Russian Language", "Encyclopedic Dictionary of Economics and Law", "Dictionary of Literary Terms", "Explanatory Dictionary of Foreign Words", "Dictionary of Youth Slang", "Brief Political Dictionary", "Semenov's Etymological Dictionary of the Russian Language".

The fact that many encyclopedic dictionaries repeat in various combinations is a reflection of the "turmoil", lack of clarity in the goals and actions of scientists; disorder in the consciousness of the masses.

In the "Latin-Russian Dictionary" we read: "conception 1) connection, sum, aggregate, system; 2) reservoir, storage; 3) formulation (edition) of legal acts; 4) conception, acceptance of seed; 5) verbal expression" [12]. This is a verbal expression, formulation of a plan, idea

(system of ideas), which contains a call to begin action on some issue, direction. That is, the concept contains the leading idea and requires mandatory expression. This is the main sought-after material, since the term "concept" itself, therefore, arose precisely on the basis of the Latin word. And this means that this explanation should be considered its real root. And reference sources, to one degree or another repeating each other, only try to give a certain interpretation, expanding or narrowing the real meaning of the concept of "concept".

In our opinion, of all the previous reference sources, the closest to the Latin source is the explanation from the Dictionary and Reference Book of Higher Education (Oliy ta'lim malumotnoma lugati), in which we read: "Concept (from Latin - "idrokplash") - 1) a system of views on processes and events in nature and society; 2) a leading idea that determines the strategy of actions. (Concept (from Latin - "understanding") - 1) a system of views on processes and events in nature and society; 2) a leading idea that determines the strategy of actions. This is knowledge, awareness, development of an idea, which is a strategy of action (actions), leading to the implementation (realization, implementation) of reforms in any direction.

We are talking about the point of view on the processes occurring in society, as well as about the "leading idea" that determines the strategy of further actions to implement certain plans, projects, reforms. As we can see, from the reference materials we have reviewed, this explanation is closest to the real etymology of the concept of "concept".

The authoritative "Dictionary of Pedagogical Terms" gives the following explanation of the "concept of education": "a system of views on certain phenomena, processes, a way of understanding, interpreting pedagogical phenomena; the main idea of the theory of the content and organization of human education." Here the concept is already associated with the theory of the content and organization of the educational process itself. That is, the explanation looks narrower, and the idea is aimed at the process of educating the individual.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In the above definitions from reference dictionaries, the following key words can be identified in relation to the "concept": system, idea, main idea. This means that in these authoritative sources on pedagogy, the basis of the concept of "concept" is precisely these three key words-concepts.

It should be noted that of the numerous sources we reviewed, only in the "Scientific and Pedagogical Glossary of an Economics Teacher" are the words "pedagogical" and "concept" given in a single combination, and the following definition is given to this concept: "A pedagogical concept is a certain way of understanding and interpreting pedagogical phenomena; the main point of view on the subject of pedagogical science or a pedagogical phenomenon, fact; a guiding idea for their systematic coverage; a system of interconnected and following from each other views of a scientist, teacher on the essence of pedagogical phenomena." That is, we are talking about the dynamics, the evolution of an idea regarding pedagogy as an idea of an individual scientist or teacher on the subject or object of pedagogy from the moment of its origin until it reaches maturity for use in pedagogical practice. True, the concept is defined from the point of view of teaching academic disciplines in economics.

Next to this glossary, the concept of "pedagogical views" is given. It is defined as follows: "Pedagogical views are opinions, judgments regarding pedagogical phenomena that have not developed into a holistic and independent concept." If we compare both explanations, it turns out that a pedagogical concept is a more specific, precise concept than pedagogical views. That is, pedagogical views are the beginnings of a "pedagogical concept", retain variability and

imply revision. "Views" are not yet generalizations, there is no harmony here yet. Only deeply thought-out ideas crystallize and grow to the state of a concept. The search for a comprehensive definition has led us to some serious scientific works created in recent decades.

In one of these works we came across the term "pedagogical concept" - this is a monograph by Russian scientists E.V. Yakovlev and N.O. Yakovleva "Pedagogical concept: methodological aspects of construction". In the work, "pedagogical concept" is defined as "a form of presentation of the result of scientific and pedagogical research and an apparatus for solving certain problems of education." The authors of the monograph drew attention to the formation of a pedagogical concept that would ensure the interconnection and theoretical basis of scientific developments of various scientists in solving current problems of pedagogy. That is, here the pedagogical concept is presented as a certain specific basis that serves to highlight the main components of the pedagogical problems being studied. In the glossary of the monograph we read the following explanation: "A pedagogical concept is a complex, purposeful, dynamic system of fundamental knowledge about a pedagogical phenomenon, fully and comprehensively revealing its essence, content, features, as well as the technology of operating with it in the context of modern education." As can be seen, the concept defines a set of conditions, measures for the effective functioning of the proposed pedagogical idea, which will be aimed at developing the learning process in an educational institution. There are a number of other works in which the concept is considered as a system of verification, research, and study of certain aspects of the pedagogical process. Let us give several examples. In the works of P.I. Tretyakov "School Management Based on Results: Practice of Pedagogical Management", T.K. Smykovskaya "Theoretical and Methodological Foundations of Designing a Methodological System for a Teacher of Mathematics and Computer Science", O.B. Epishcheva "Activity Approach as a Theoretical Basis for Designing a Methodological System for Teaching Mathematics", M.N. Nevzorov "Theoretical Foundations of Designing an Anthropocentric Pedagogical Process", V.E. Rodionov "Theoretical Foundations of Pedagogical Design" there is a different interpretation of the concept of "concept". Thus, the "concept of school development management" developed by P.I. Tretyakov includes as structural components analytical justification, relevance, goals and objectives, the essence of the concept, updating the content of education, the structure of the educational process, the system of intra-school management, as well as a forecast of the final results of the school's activities. The concept proposed by T.K. Smykovskaya consists of "principles of designing and organizing monitoring of the formation, development, and functioning of the teacher's methodological system, didactic requirements for teaching design, a system of models that ensure design activities."

Noting the scientific value and significance of the results obtained by the authors, we come to the conclusion that the views of the scientists whose works we studied concerned more the concept of education, rather than pedagogy in general. From all of the above, we can conclude that in the definition of the term "concept", the key concepts are "system", "intention", "main leading idea" that determines the strategy of thinking, creative and practical actions on a particular issue. With regard to the "pedagogical concept", these are not just thoughts, but a holistic system of interconnected and flowing from each other views of a scientist, teacher on the essence of pedagogical phenomena. This is a more specific, precise concept than pedagogical views. That is, pedagogical views are the beginnings of the

"pedagogical concept", retain variability and imply revision, without constituting a specific system. "Views" are not generalizations yet, they do not imply any practical actions, and relate more to the theoretical part of the pedagogical process. And the concept dictates the implementation of specific targeted programs and actions that lead to a radical change and a specific result.

Based on the results of the analysis, we derive the following concept: the pedagogical concept of the writer is the leading idea of the artistic motive, on the basis of which special statements, interconnected and interdependent ideas aimed at solving pedagogical problems are built.

Based on this, we believe that before the pedagogical concept of the writer is comprehended by the reader, becomes his intellectual property, it, being the embryo of potential mental constructs - impressions, sensations, ideas - are certainly experienced at the level of the unconscious. The reader does not classify the components of the material being mastered (into social, economic, pedagogical, etc.), but gets acquainted with the content. But as the analysis proceeds in depth, which involves thought processes, the ideas implied by the author of the work are gradually extracted by consciousness from the unconscious. Then the real concepts crystallize into certain clear semantic fragments, reflecting the results of the feelings and impressions worked out by the writer. In this way, the writer's pedagogical concept is learned.

With regard to the work of Ch. Aitmatov, the following definition can be formulated: the pedagogical concept of Ch. Aitmatov is a set of pedagogical ideas of the writer, representing a holistic system of views on the essence of pedagogical phenomena. It should be noted that this concept does not exist in its finished form. The constituent elements of the pedagogical concept of Ch. Aitmatov were originally realized in his journalistic articles and works of art. Our task is to identify and systematize the pedagogical ideas of the writer, trace their dynamics and form a single concept.

We believe that the internationalism and deep philosophical nature of the ideas of Ch. Aitmatov makes his pedagogical concept universal, understandable and relevant for every nation and finds echoes in the people's consciousness. Ch. Aitmatov helps readers not only in comprehending the basics of pedagogy, but also in searching for and finding their own self-awareness through comprehending knowledge about their roots, ancestors and their rich spiritual and moral heritage.

CONCLUSION. The pedagogical concept of Ch. Aitmatov must certainly be considered in the context of the contemporary state of the pedagogical process (to substantiate the author's pedagogical ideas) and the current pressing issues of upbringing and education (for the practical application of concepts). Therefore, we decided to first analyze the prerequisites for the formation of Ch. Aitmatov's pedagogical thought before proceeding to the study of his journalism and artistic creativity.

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